

Title: **Scoping Review** Protocol for Health Literacy among Older Immigrants

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1. Background

Health literacy is a critical determinant of an individual's ability to understand and navigate the healthcare system, make informed decisions about their health, and effectively manage their health conditions. Older immigrants, a growing and diverse population, may face unique challenges related to health literacy due to language barriers, cultural differences, and the complexities of the healthcare systems in their host countries. Understanding the state of research on health literacy among older immigrants is essential for informing healthcare policies and interventions to better serve this population.

2. Objective

The objective of this scoping review is to systematically map and synthesize existing literature on health literacy among older migrants. This review aims to provide an overview of the key themes, results, and concepts in the current body of research related to the health literacy of older migrants, in order to guide future research and inform healthcare practices and policies. The proposed review will be guided by the methodological framework proposed by Arksey and O'Malley (2005). Thus, the following five steps will be followed in this scoping review: (i) identifying the research question, (ii) identifying relevant studies, (iii) selection of eligible studies, (iv) charting the data, and (v) collating and summarising the results.

3. Research Questions

The scoping review will seek to answer the following research questions:

- a. What is the current state of knowledge on health literacy among older immigrants?
- b. What are the key themes, concepts, and definitions related to health literacy among older immigrants? How was health literacy studied? Which concepts and definitions of health literacy have been applied?
- c. What are the factors and determinants influencing health literacy among older immigrants?

4. Search Strategy

A comprehensive search strategy will be developed to identify relevant literature. The search will include the following databases:

- Medline (Ovid)
- Embase (embase.com)
- Web of Science (Clarivate Analytics)
- CINAHL (EBSCO)

- PsycInfo (EBSCO)
- Reference lists of included studies

The search strategy will be developed in Medline (Ovid) in collaboration with librarians at the Karolinska Institutet University Library. For each search concept Medical Subject Headings (MeSH-terms) and free text terms will be identified. The strategies will be peer reviewed by another librarian prior to execution.

The search terms will be a combination of keywords and Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) terms, including "health literacy," "human migration", "Emigrants and Immigrants", "Transients and Migrants", "Refugees/", "Refugee Camps/", "migrants", "aged/" Boolean operators (AND, OR) will be used to refine the search strategy.

5. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Studies will be included in the review if they meet the following criteria:

Inclusion Criteria:

- Studies that are available as full texts
- Published in English, German or Swedish
- Published between 2012 and 2023
- Primary sources such as original studies
- Peer-reviewed
- Health Literacy was measured
- Older immigrants or people with immigration experience (65 years or older)
- Older refugees or people who had experienced displacement (65 years or older)
- Focus on health literacy among older immigrants (65 years or older) or discussing specific health literacy results for this age group

Exclusion Criteria:

- Studies not available as full texts
- Published in other languages as English, German or Swedish
- Published before 2012 or after 2023
- Secondary sources such as literature reviews
- Not peer-reviewed
- Health literacy was not measured, or only specific health literacy measurements were applied such as mental health literacy or diabetes health literacy
- Younger immigrants or people with immigration experience (under 65 years)
- Younger refugees or people who had experienced displacement (under 65 years)
- People without any kind of migration experience
- Studies unrelated to health literacy among older immigrants

6. Data Extraction

We will use Covidence, a web-based software platform, to complete our scoping review (<https://www.covidence.org>). Following the inclusion and exclusion criteria at least two reviewers will scan the abstracts in a first step and the remaining article as full texts. Conflicts will be solved between two reviewers. The data to be extracted will include study characteristics, population demographics and key findings. One reviewer will conduct the data extraction process, with any discrepancies resolved through discussion or consultation with at least a second reviewer. The data extraction chart will be discussed with the other reviewers.

7. Data Analysis and Synthesis

A narrative synthesis approach will be employed to summarize the findings from the included studies. Thematic analysis will be used to identify key themes, concepts, and factors related to health literacy among older immigrants. The results will be presented in a descriptive and thematic manner, including tables, charts, and textual summaries.

8. Quality Appraisal

The scoping review will not assess the quality of included studies, as the goal is to map the existing literature rather than assess the strength of evidence.

9. Dissemination

The findings of this scoping review will be disseminated through a peer-reviewed publication, presentations, and other relevant platforms.

10. Ethical Considerations

This scoping review will not involve human subjects, and therefore, ethical approval is not required.

11. Timelines

The scoping review will be conducted between October 2023 to May 2024.

12. Conclusion

This protocol outlines the methodology for conducting a scoping review on health literacy among older immigrants. The review will provide a comprehensive overview of the existing literature, identify key themes, and results in the research related to older immigrants.